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GLOBALIZATION AND ITS IMPACT ON BUSINESS, CUSTOMERS & ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

Now a day's almost every aspect of human life and activity is somewhere influenced by globalization e.g. life-style, culture, education, occupation etc. In same way, impact of globalization is also present in various activities of many industries such as medical-health care, manufacturing industries, telecommunication industries, textile industry, hotel & tourism industry etc. Globalization is a very broad concept which involves sharing of ideas, philosophy, techniques, technology, capital investment, market etc. In this research paper, descriptive and research methodology is used to explain the characteristic, objective, trends, drivers and impact of globalization on business(firms/companies ,its customers as well as on the economy of nation. Impacts of globalization may be favorable or unfavorable for a business and marketing activities. This research article also shows effect of globalization on economy development of a nation.

Key Words: Globalization, customers, economy, global trading, MNCs.

INTRODUCTION

Globalization is considered one of the most important drivers of new economy. Globalization is not a new concept but has notably developed in last quarter of 20th century. "Globalization" is a term that came into popular usage in the 1980's to describe the increased movement of people, knowledge and ideas, and goods and money across national borders that has led to increased interconnectedness among the world's populations, economically, politically, socially and culturally. Although globalization is often thought of in economic terms (i.e. the global marketplace), this process has many social and political implications as well. Many in local communities associate globalization with modernization. At the global level, globalization is thought of in terms of the challenges it poses to the role of governments in international affairs and the global economy. In other words it can be said that globalization is a powerful driver of world economy that poses advantage and some difficulties for business and marketing practices.

MEANING AND CONCEPT OF GLOBALIZATION:

Globalization is the shift towards a more integrated and interdependent world economy. Globalization has two main components- the globalization of markets and the globalization of production. Globalization implies the opening of local and nationalistic perspectives to a broader outlook of an interconnected and interdependent world with free transfer of capital, goods, and services across national frontiers. However, it does not include unhindered movement of labor and, as suggested by some economists, may hurt smaller or fragile economies if applied indiscriminately. Globalization is the growing economic interdependence of countries worldwide through increasing volume and variety of cross border transactions in goods and services and of international capital flows and also through the more rapid and widespread diffusion of technology.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM:

Globalization is a very broad and very influential phenomenon. The concept of globalization is an old one that has different interpretations to different people. Partly as a result of these different implementations, there are very different reactions to “globalization”, with some policy maker, scholars, and activists seeing it as a force for advancing the world economy while others, again all three, seeing it as a serious danger to the world economic system due to its unfavorable characteristics. Therefore it is important to develop a common and standardized understanding of globalization so that the advantage that comes with globalization can be availed to maximum and demerits of globalization can be avoided or reduced as much as possible.

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY:

This research throws a light on the phenomenon of globalization by describing the characteristics, objective, trends and factor effecting globalization. This research study also explains the impact of globalization on consumers, various business activities and national economy of a country. This research paper will help in better understanding of impact of globalization by classifying various effect of globalization into advantageous and disadvantageous effects of globalization.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

- Abramovitz, M. (1986) stated that doubts can be cast about the belief that globalizationshould always benefit employment growth.
- Grossman, G.M. and Helpman, E. (1991), found that in addition to innovation, globalization plays a vital role in economic development of underdeveloped and developing countries only if now technology is a ‘appropriate technology’.
- Lee, E. (1996), found that globalization has a positive effect on growth of manufacturing industry of Asian countries.
- Basu, S. and D.N. Weil (1998) concluded that irrespective of globalization and technology transfer, lack of local capabilities can severely jeopardize the potential for economic and employment growth.
- Collier, P. and Dollar, D. (2002) stated that ss far as poverty reduction is concerned, trade, FDI and globalization are supposed to be beneficial to a developing country’s economic growth
- Lall S. (2004), concluded that when a developing country opens its borders to foreign capital, FDI’s generate positive employment impacts both directly and indirectly through job creation within suppliers and retailers and also a tertiary employment effect through generating additional incomes ultimately increasing aggregate demand.
- Eddy Lee and Marco Vivarelli (2006) concluded that in developing countries impact of globalization in terms of income distribution, growth, employment generation and various business activities is very high.
- Farha, A. (2009) concluded that its is mandatory for a firm to develop a product for a target market taking in consideration the effects of globalization.
- Dukeil M. (2010) concluded that globalization has a very high influence on needs and desires of customers in a developing country.
- Kapil, S. (2011) found that globalization is a ongoing phenomenon influencing almost every aspect of business and trading. He suggested that globalization may act as a opportunity for some nations and companies while may act as a threat for others.
- James Scriven (2014) found that that consumers appear to automatically conduct more research on products generally looking for the best deal. Consistent with his notion is the result that when it comes to certain products, brand name is not always the primary determinant for consumer choice.

METHODOLOGY:

This study is descriptive in nature. On the basis of time-dimension this research is cross-sectional in nature because it explains the phenomenon of globalization at one point in time, i.e. the present day scenario.

Data Collection: This research study is primarily based on secondary data. The sources of secondary data are

- Official web-sites and news-letters published by Multi-National Companies from various industrial sectors. In retail sector Wall-Mart, in manufacturing industry Coalgate, in auto-mobile industry Volkswagen, in health-care industry Hamd Medical Corporation and in service industry Cox & Kings.
- Published research articles in various management journals.
- Published articles in Business Magazines.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

Globalization is ongoing, continuous and persistent phenomenon throughout the world. Globalization can be understood as a highly influential force that effect all aspect of business activities. Globalization is also responsible for the major increases in worldwide trade and exchanges in an increasingly open, integrated and borderless international economy. There has been remarkable growth in such trade and exchanges of goods & services, capital & currencies, technology transfer and international flow of information and ideas.

CHARECTERISTIC OF GLOBALISATION: There are following key characteristics of globalization:

- Liberalization: The freedom of the industrialist/businessman to establish industry, trade or commerce either in his country or abroad; free exchange of capital, goods, service and technologies between countries.
- Free Trade: Free trade between countries; absence of excessive governmental control over trade.
- Globalization of Economic Activities: Control of economic activities by domestic market and international market; coordination of national economy and world economy.
- Connectivity: Localities being connected with the world by breaking national boundaries; forging of links between one society and another, and between one country and another through international transmission of knowledge, literature, technology, culture and information.
- Borderless Globe: Breaking of national barriers and creation of inter- connectedness; the ideal of 'borderless globe' articulated by Kenichi Ohmae.
- A Composite Process: Integration of nation-states across the world by common economic, commercial, political, cultural and technological ties; creation of a new world order with no national boundaries.
- A Multi-dimensional Process: Economically, it means opening up of national market, free trade and commerce among nations, and integration of national economies with the world economy. Politically, it means limited powers and functions of state, more rights and freedoms granted to the individual and empowerment of private sector; culturally, it means exchange of cultural values between societies and between nations; and ideologically, it means the spread of liberalism and capitalism.

OBJECTIVE OF GLOBALIZATION:

There are following objectives of globalization:

- To Provide Wide Choices: Globalization aims for providing wide range of choices that are available in the market today. Earlier foreign goods were a rarity and if at all they were available they were extremely expensive. Today the scene has completely changed. There are varieties and varieties of goods from the groceries to beauty products to other consumer goods in all sections of the market.

- To Unite Cultures: Globalization aims at uniting people around the world by promoting a common culture and frame of reference. The people of different culture are able to learn about each other, they can overcome misconception about other cultures and develop a universal harmony among them.
- To Facilitate Free Flow of Capital: Globalization helps for free flow of capital from one country to the other. It helps the investors to get a fair interest rates or dividend and the global companies to acquire finance at lower cost of capital. Further, globalization increase capital flow surplus countries to the needy countries, which in turn increases the global investment.
- To Increase Industrialization: Free flow of capital, along with the technology enables the developing countries to boost-up industrialization in their countries. This ultimately increases global industrialization.
- To Create Jobs: globalization aims at creating jobs and fostering economic growth in those developing countries willing to open their economies for foreign investment. Open economies leads to more jobs, higher wages and better standards of living.
- To Boost Economy: The objective of globalization is not limited to increase import and export goods but also to allow for outsourcing services and jobs. Jobs in information technology sector are especially outsourced as an important section of globalization. Many developed countries setup branches in developing countries because the labour is relatively cheap in developing countries as compared to their mother country. So the result is direct increase in their net profits. And for developing countries they get a sudden burst of jobs with help in economic growth of developing country.

TRENDS IN GLOBALIZATION

Current trends are towards the increasing globalization and interdependence of firms, markets and countries. Intense competition among countries, industries and firms on global level is a recent development owed to the confluence of several major trends which are as follows:

- Cooperation Among Countries: Countries cooperates with each other in thousands of way through international organizations, treaties and consultations. Such cooperation generally encourages the globalization of business by eliminating restrictions on it and by outlining frameworks that reduce uncertainties about what companies will and will not be allowed to do. Countries cooperate to gain reciprocal advantages, to attack problems they cannot solve alone and to deal with concerns that lie outside anyone's territory. Agreements on variety of commercially related activities, such as transportation and trade, allows nation to gain advantages. In addition, countries cooperate on problems they cannot solve, such as by coordinating national economic programs so the global economic conditions are minimally disrupted, and by restricting import of certain products to protect endangered species. Finally countries set agreements how to commercially exploit areas outside any of their territories These include outer space (such as on transmission of television programs), non-coastal areas of oceans and seas.
- Liberalization of Cross-Border Movements: Every country restricts the movement across its borders of goods and services as well as the resources, such as workers and capital, to produce them. Such restrictions make international business cumbersome. Further, because the restriction may change at any time, the ability to sustain international business is always uncertain. However, governments today impose fewer restrictions on cross-border movements than they did a decade or two ago, allowing companies to better take advantage of international opportunities. Governments have decreased restrictions because they believe that:
 - (a) Open economies will give consumers better access to a greater variety of goods and services at lower prices.
 - (b) Producers will become more efficient by competing against foreign companies.
 - (c) If they reduce their own restrictions, other countries will do the same.

- **Transfer of Technology:** Technology transfer is the process by which commercial technology is disseminated. This will take the form of a technology transfer transaction which may or may not be a legally binding contract, but which will involve the communication, by the transferor, of relevant knowledge to the recipient. The reasons behind encouragement of transfer of technology by companies are as follows:
 - (a) The biggest reason for transfer of technology is profit. Many companies sell their technology to earn a profit. It can be understood by following example; after Second World War, Kodak had to quit Japanese market due to certain restrictions. But then Kodak started selling its technology to Japanese firms like Konika and Fuji.
 - (b) Technology is transferred as production may be cheaper abroad and output does not have to be transported over long distances to reach the end consumer.
 - (c) To gain competitive edge in foreign markets through the supply of technically superior product.
 - (d) Many underdeveloped and developing countries give various incentives to MNCs to invite them and relative advanced technology into their country.
 - (e) To exploit superior capital markets, access to skilled labour and other inputs in foreign countries.
 - (f) To enhance the competence and potential of foreign subsidiaries.

DRIVERS/FACTORS EFFECTING GLOBALIZATION

There are following major forces behind globalization:

- **Increase and Expansion of Technology:** Conducting business on an international level usually involves greater distances than does conducting domestic business, and greater distances increase operating costs and make control of company's foreign operation more difficult. But improved communications and transportation speed up interactions and improve a manager's ability to control foreign operation.
- **Liberalization of Cross Border Trade and Resource Movements:** To protect its own industries, every country restricts the movement across its borders of goods and services and the resources, such as workers and capital, to produce both. Such restrictions make international business more expensive to undertake. Because the regulations may change any time, international business is also riskier. However, over time most governments have lowered some restrictions on trade for the following reasons:
 - (a) Their citizens have expressed the desire for easier access to a greater variety of goods and services at lower prices.
 - (b) To make domestic producers more efficient by making them competing with foreign producers.
- **Development of Services that Support International Business:** Companies and government have developed services that ease the conduct of international business. Although companies do barter internationally, it can be cumbersome, time-consuming, risky and expensive. Today most companies are paid relatively easily for goods and services sold abroad because of bank credit agreements, clearing arrangements that convert one country's currency into another's and insurance that covers risks like damage enroute and non-payments by the buyer.
- **Growing Consumer Pressure:** Because of innovations in transportation and communications, consumers know about products and services available in other countries. Further global discretionary income has risen to the point there is now widespread demand for products and services that would have been considered luxuries in the past. Thus, consumers want more, new, better and differentiated products. However, this greater affluence has not been evenly spread either among or within countries, thus companies have recently responded more to those markets, such as China, where incomes and consumption are growing most rapidly.
- **Increased Global Competition:** Consumers have more discretionary income, which means that dissimilar products and services compete for the same consumer expenditure. This expansion of

competition, forces most companies to seek any means to gain competitive advantages, including a global search for quality improvement or cost reduction advantages.

- **Changing Political Situation:** A major reason of growth of international business has been the end of breach between most communist and non-communist countries. Even within the communist bloc, countries strove to be as self-sufficient as possible, with the transformation of political and economic policies in the former Soviet Union, most of Eastern Europe, China and Vietnam, trade now flourishes between those countries and the rest of the world.

IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION:

There are various effects of globalization on a business and its customer as well as on other stakeholders also. The impact of globalization on these parties may be advantageous or disadvantageous for them.

ADVANTAGES OF GLOBALIZATION: Benefits (advantages) of globalization on a business, customers and economy of a nation are as follows:

- **Goods & Services:** As markets become more global, more goods and services are made available at lower cost to wider group of people. More access leads to rising consumer demand and improved standards of living. In addition, global competition and cheap imports keep a lid on prices, so that inflation is less likely to derail economic growth.
- **Financial Markets:** Economic growth requires investment capital. Globalised capital market attract investors to the most favorable financial markets and “hot growth” economies, thereby allowing investors to maximize their return.
- **Governments:** By connecting people to the outside world, globalization breaks down isolation. Advocates claim that instant people-to-people communication spreads democracy and leads to fall of dictatorship.
- **Conflicts:** The more economically interdependent the world becomes, the more people will trade and communicate with one another. This leads to inherent stability, where disputes are more likely to be resolved peacefully.
- **Free flow of technology:** As started earlier, globalization helps for the flow of technology from advanced countries to the developing countries. It helps the developing countries to implement new technology.
- **Spread up of Production Facilities Throughout the global countries** depending upon the location and various favorable production factors.
- **Balanced Development of Worlds Economies:** With the flow of capital, technology and locating manufacturing facilities in developing countries, the developing countries industrialize the economies. This in turn leads to the balanced development of all the countries.
- **Increase in Production and Consumption:** Increased industrialization in globe leads increase in production and thus results in balanced industrial development along with increases in income which enhances level of consumption.
- **Lower Prices with High Quality:** Indian consumers have already been getting the products of high quality at lower prices. Increased industrialization, spread up of technology, increased production and consumption level enables the companies to produce and sell the products of high quality at lower prices.
- **Cultural Exchange and Demand for a Variety of Products:** Globalization reduces the physical distances among the countries and enables people of different countries to acquire the culture of other countries. The cultural exchange, in turn makes the people to demand for a variety of products which are being consumed in other countries.
- Globalization also causes increase employment, increased income and balanced human development.

DISADVANTAGES OF GLOBALIZATION: There are following limitation/harmful effect of globalization on s business, customers and economy of a nation:

- **Reduced Jobs and Incomes:** One major criticism against globalization is that compared to creating jobs it is actually destroys manufacturing jobs in countries like India and China. These critics argue that, falling trade barriers allows the firms to move their manufacturing activities to countries where wage rates are much lower.
- **Poor Labour Practices and Environmental Policies:** One of the criticisms against globalization is that free trade encourages developed nations to move manufacturing facilities off-shore to less developed countries that lack adequate regulations to protect labour and environment.
- **National Sovereignty Getting Limited:** With the development of the World Trade Organization and other multilateral organizations, countries and localities necessarily give up some authority over their actions. If a nation wanted to retreat into a more protectionist position, it could clearly choose to withdraw from its international agreements.
- **Reluctance of Developed Countries:** Though advocating the advantages of a free market mechanism and competitive markets, rich economies of the world are themselves riddle with all sorts of distortions on account of monopoly forces, huge subsidies and a variety of vested interests. They are not ready to accommodate the poorer countries of the world on criteria of economic fairness.
- **Short Term Gains:** Many researchers argue that long run sustainable growth and prosperity of the developed countries can be ensured only by the growing prosperity of the developing countries, the former are not ready to adopt and pursue this approach. Instead they are always eagerly looking for opportunities to reap short-term gains.
- **Non-Economic Hurdles:** Any form of economic integration, by its very nature, necessitates a corresponding compromise of national sovereignty and it is more in case of global economic integration. This poses a great difficulty and often unacceptable choice for national governments.
- **Factor Mobility:** Globalization facilitates unhindered international factor mobility. Developing nations feel that unrestricted mobility of capital and finance can be damaging for them. While developed countries are apprehensive about the unrestricted immigration of low-wage labour.
- **Big corporate entities have a tendency to kill competition and dominate markets.** Developing countries are apprehensive that such practice would inflict large scale and long term damage to their agriculture, small scale and cottage industry and employment.
- **Consumerism:** Developing country also rightly fear that unbridled globalization would feed consumerism and retard domestic savings and capital accumulation. A country with low per capita income cannot afford to let this happen.
- **Social Security:** With globalization, it becomes increasingly difficult for a government (particularly for developing country) to create finance a social security system. Such like provisions tend to lose their priority in market-oriented globalization.
- **Risk & Uncertainties:** Progress toward globalization is also hindered by uncertainties relating to a possible shift in political and economic philosophy of some member countries. The fear of nationalization by the MNCs, the resistance to cultural invasion associated with unrestricted inflow of foreign capital and enterprise and so on.

CONCLUSION & SUGGESTION:

Globalization is the worldwide movement toward economic, technological, trade, and communication integration. Globalization implies the opening of local and nationalistic perspectives to a broader outlook of an interconnected and interdependent world with free transfer of capital, goods, and services across national frontiers. The ultimate aim of globalization are to provide wide choices to companies and customers, to unite different culture, facilitate free flow of capital and to aid in increasing national income of the country. The reason of occurrence of globalization is sharing of technology, liberalization of cross-border trade, improved

communication resulting in improved awareness of customers etc. However, it does not include unhindered movement of labor and, as suggested by some economists, may hurt smaller or fragile economies if applied indiscriminately. Globalization act as a advantages for many business and nations but it doesn't mean globalization always act in favor of them. Some aspect globalization also poses problem for developing country economy and its companies/producers. So it is very important for every nation to identify, analyze and understand the phenomenon of globalization in order to avail its maximum advantage and minimize its disadvantageous effects. The same implies for every companies (especially MNCs) to development of product appropriately customers and to develop its marketing strategy considering various aspect of globalization in mind, such as technological, communication, global integrations, liberalization etc.

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